



Panel C



Panel E

Fig. 3, Panel C,E



Panel G



Panel I



Panel K



Fig. 4, Panel G, I, K



Panel D



Panel H

Fig. 7, Panel D, H



Panel D



Panel F

Fig. 8, Panel D, F